

Elemental analysis of seagrass and sediment

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Fe, Zn, Cu, Pb, Mn, Ni, Co, Al, P and S have been analyzed by ICP-AES. The levels of elements are compared between the sea sediment and seagrass. Fe is the highest metal found in both sea sediment and seagrass. Considerable levels of Al, Mn, P and S are also found in both. The levels of the elements analyzed can be divided into three categories : elements that are higher in sediment than seagrass, elements that are equal in both and elements that are lower in sediment than seagrass.

In the tropical Australia, seagrasses are essential food for dugong, *Dugong dugon* (Müller), and green sea turtles, *Chelonia mydas* Linnaeus. Elemental analysis has not been carried out extensively on these seagrasses. The knowledge of elemental composition may be important for those studies related to the animals feeding on the seagrasses. This is especially true for the dugong where the levels of metals in the tissues were found to be extremely high compared to other sea mammals¹. The present paper attempt to explain the relationship that may exist between the element in the sea sediment and seagrass.

Results and Discussion

Elements in sediments :

The elemental analysis of each of the four samples (S-1 to S-4) of sea sediments was determined in triplicate. There is a considerable variation in the concentration of elements analyzed in each sample. The summary of the mean values for all of the elements is shown in Table I. These give an indication on the variations of elements in different sampled areas. The mean values and standard deviations refer to the elemental composition of the area as a whole that supports the seagrasses.

The four samples of sea sediments consistently displayed the concentrations of iron that were higher than any other element analyzed. The iron concentration ranges from 11313 to 20347 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ dry weight. These values are considerably lower than the values reported by Batley² (about 40000 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ dry weight) in studies of heavy metal speciation in Lake Macquarie, 100 km north of Sydney (NSW, Australia). This area has experienced a deterioration in the quality of the water due to the presence of lead-zinc smelter and other industry.

The level of aluminum in the present study is consider-

Table I. Mean concentration ($\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ dry wt.) of selected elements in sediments samples (S1-S4)

Element	S-1	S-2	S-3	S-4	Mean	S.E.M.
Fe	20347	17995	18662	11313	17079	1146
Al	8734	6460	7183	5191	6892	427
Mn	238	190	188	195	203	7
Cu	12	8	5	3	7	1.2
Zn	17	14	15	15	15	0.3
P	163	112	337	64	169	34
S	5191	4996	5002	3826	4754	180
Pb	23	10	5	19	14	2.3
Cd	1	1	0	1	1	0.3
Ni	10	9	7	4	8	0.9
Co	0	4	4	1	2	0.6

able. It ranges from 5191 to 8734 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ dry weight. An appreciable level of manganese is present in all the sediments. The level of sulfur is also very high. Sample variation is not very great (S.E.M. = 180). The concentration ranges between 3826 and 5191 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ dry weight. A notable amount of phosphorus is present in the sediments. The difference between samples is large. The concentration ranges between 64 and 337 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ dry weight. Zinc is present with a mean value of 15 g g^{-1} dry weight. There is little variation among the four samples of sediment for zinc.

Other metals such as copper, lead, cadmium, nickel and cobalt are detected at very low concentrations. All of these elements have concentrations less than 10 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ dry weight. Cadmium in sample S-3 and cobalt in sample S-1 is below the detection limit of the elements.

Elements in seagrasses :

There were six bags of seagrass that were taken from Northern Territory. Each bag contained a mixture of three

species of seagrasses. They were identified as *Halodule univervis*, *Halodule pinifolia* and *Syringodium isoentifolium* according to classification by Larkum and den Hartog³. These seagrasses are some preferred by dugongs living in the area⁴⁻⁷. The three different species (whole plant) were mixed and ground into dry powder. Each sample consisted of a mixture of the three species of seagrass.

Triplicate determinations of each of the twelve elements were carried out. A summary of the mean of six sample (S-1 to S-6) for each element is shown in Table 2. The mean value and standard deviation were calculated to give an indication on the levels of each element in the area from where the seagrasses were collected.

Table 2. Mean concentration ($\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ dry wt.) of selected elements in seagrass

Element	S-1	S-2	S-3	S-4	S-5	S-6	Mean	S.E.M.
Fe	4437	9956	5239	11479	1982	2244	5890	936
Al	1185	1809	1423	2350	894	900	1427	134
Mn	204	327	114	270	269	209	232	17
Cu	3	6	13	6	4	4	6	0.9
Zn	10	11	7	26	9	10	12	1.6
P	1072	903	1221	759	886	880	954	39
S	8860	7477	15846	8801	13166	13131	11214	777
Pb	3	4	0	7	8	0	4	0.7
Cd	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	0.2
Ni	7	9	9	5	7	5	7	0.5
Co	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0

The most abundant element found in all the seagrasses analyzed in the present study, except sample S-2 and sample S-4, is sulfur. The sample variation ranges between 7477 and 15846 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ dry weight. Sulfur is content in amino acids cystine, cysteine and methionine, and hence it enters as the composition of some proteins. This may contribute to the high level of sulfur in the leaves of the seagrasses.

The highest concentration of metal in the seagrass is iron. The variation between samples is considerable. The concentration ranges from 1982 to 11479 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ dry weight. The concentrations of iron of seagrasses examined are considerably higher than the average value of 140 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ dry weight reported by Bowen⁸ for terrestrial plants. Pasture grasses usually contain 100–200 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ dry weight⁹. Linne *et al.*¹⁰ noted the iron values in excess of 2000 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ dry weight for species of fresh-water grasses. Therefore, it seems that in general, the iron content of seagrass is much higher than that of terrestrial species. The levels of aluminum and phosphorus are notable. Aluminum is present in the range 894–2350 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ dry weight. Phosphorus levels are slightly

lower, ranging between 759 and 1221 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ dry weight. A considerable concentration of manganese is found in all the samples of seagrasses. The variation between samples is considerable and the levels of manganese are in the range 114–327 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ dry weight. Zinc is present in detectable amount. The mean value is 12 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ dry weight. Other metals that are present at low levels include copper, lead, cadmium and nickel. Cobalt is hardly detected except in sample S-5.

The levels of element in sediment and seagrass are summarized and compared as shown in Figs. 1 and 2. Evidently, the elements analyzed can be categorized into three groups. The first group is the levels of element higher in sediment than in seagrass; these include iron, aluminum, zinc, nickel, copper and lead. The second group : manganese and cadmium are present almost in equal amount in sediment and seagrass. The last group : those elements that are lower in sediment than in seagrass. In his last group, phosphorus and sulfur are non-metal and are essential to plant as integral part of protein in the leave of a plant. Cobalt is not detected in seagrass and cannot be compared with the level in sediment. The levels of metals in the present study are comparable to that found in a similar study of seagrasses in North Queensland¹.

Conclusion :

The selected elements analyzed in the sediment and

Fig. 1. Concentration of selected elements of sediment and seagrass : Fe, Al, Mn, P and S.

Fig. 2. Concentration of selected elements of sediment and seagrass : Cu, Zn, Pb, Cd, Ni and Co.

seagrass vary considerably. There are elements that are present at higher levels in sediment than in seagrass. These elements include iron, aluminum, zinc, nickel, copper and lead. The high level of iron and aluminum in seagrass may be due to the presence of high level of these two metals in the sediment. Zinc, nickel and copper are required in trace amount in plant. Lead is a non-essential element and its presence in the sediment may be causing it to be absorbed into the seagrass.

Manganese and cadmium are present at almost equal amounts in both sediment and seagrass. Manganese is involved in nitrogen metabolism and acts as cofactor in activating numerous enzymes. Cadmium is non-essential element and is present at very low level in both sediment and seagrass. Cobalt is required by plant as a constituent of vitamin B₁₂ but is not detected in the seagrass analyzed.

Phosphorus and sulfur levels are higher in seagrass than in sediment. This indicates that both of these non-metals may be transported actively into the seagrass. Phosphorus is involved in structural component of ATP, nucleic acid and phospholipids while sulfur is part of structural component of some amino acids, proteins and vitamins.

The presence of the selected elements analyzed in the sediment could undoubtedly be taken up by seagrass. They might eventually get into sea mammals that feed on seagrass.

Experimental

Source of samples : The seagrasses (6 bags) and sediments (4 bags) were donated by Antoinette Ward, an environmental officer at McArthur River Mining Pty Ltd., Northern Territory 0820, Australia. The samples were taken in the area where the dugong from Northern Territory was captured : approximately 1 km E.S.E of Dugong Creek (UTM coordinates 683800E and 8246800N). The samples were flown by air and kept cold in ice and stored at -20° until analysis. The samples were dug and collected by hand and stored in a polyethylene bag after removing adhering sediment and extraneous material as much as possible.

Analysis of sediment samples : The sediment was analyzed for total elements. Samples were prepared for analysis by digestion with concentrated nitric acid and perchloric acid. Before digestion, the sediment was freeze-dried in a freeze-drier at -50° and 2 Pa vacuum for 72 h. Drying was continued in a conventional oven at 70° to dry the sediment completely. The dried sediment was sieved to remove coarse materials such as sea shell and gravel. The sediment was stored in a polyethylene container kept in a glass desiccator under vacuum until analysis.

Each sample powder was weighed accurately (~ 100 mg) in a 100-ml acid-washed conical flask for acid digestion. A blank (conc. nitric acid, 5 ml and perchloric acid 35% (v/v, 1.0 ml) and a control (commercially prepared citrus leaves) were also included. Conc. nitric acid (5 ml) was added to the powder and heated at 70° until a clear solution was formed. The temperature was increased to 165° . Perchloric acid (35%, v/v; 1.0 ml) was then added to the clear solution and heating was continued until a white fume of perchloric acid (after ~ 1 h) evolved. At this stage, distilled water was added and the solution cooled to room temperature. The solution was made up to the mark with distilled water, then filtered to remove any undissolved silica particles. The sample was then analyzed for Fe, Zn, Cu, Pb, Mn, Ni, Co, Al, P and S by ICP-AES (inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectrometer, Varian Liberty 200 at Environmental Science, School of Biological and Environmental Science, Murdoch University).

Digestion of seagrass : The frozen seagrass was thawed in cold room at 4° overnight, then washed with deionized water to remove traces of sediments and other materials. The cleaned sample was separated into different species of seagrass and freeze-dried at -50° and 2 Pa vacuum for 72 h. Analysis of the elements was carried out on the whole seagrass that included roots, rhizomes and leaves.

The dried seagrass was ground, kept in a polyethylene

container, and stored in a glass desiccator under vacuum until required for analysis. The seagrass powder was weighed accurately (~100 mg) into an acid-washed (50 ml) conical flask for acid digestion in triplicate as that for sea sediment above and the elements were analyzed by ICP-AES.

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